

An Analysis of High Urbanization via Clustering in Iraq for Development Road Project

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ABSTRACT

High-speed mobilization is one of the most significant dynamics of transport in existing case. It is a transport mode, which stands out on mobility between urbans with high speed, high capacity, and high comfort. This mode has a vital position for tourism destinations too. It is an effective way of sustainable transport policies that supports intercity tourism links. It is also an efficient dynamic for advance of nations too. On this study, a cluster-essential analysis was performed for Iraq by using of population and similar economical indicators via cluster statistical connections. Recommendations were shared by taking into account the competitive operating distances of high capacity mobility among related cluster urbans, and results and suggestions were given on this parallel.

Keywords— Clustering analysis, urban, high speed, tourism, economy

I. INTRODUCTION

Transportation is at the heart of development, attracting tourism, social activity, economic growth, and cultural relations. Transportation services increase the emphasis on tourism travel at city, regional, national, and international levels. Today, tourism is one of the main pillars of economic development for countries.

Iraq has entered a post-war recovery process and is a significant country in Southwest Asia. It has an ancient history and a strategic location. The country stretches mainly along a north-south axis and has vast deserts. The climate is rich. It is one of the richest countries in the world in terms of oil resources. The vast majority of the country's population is Arab. In addition, there are communities such as Kurds (10%), Turkmens (10%), Shabaks (500,000), Yazidis (500,000), and Assyrians. Iraq's population is 48,007,437, its area is 434,320 km², and its urban population rate is 72.96% (Worldometer Iraq, 2026).

The population density is high, and the population growth rate is very high. Turkey is bordered by countries such as Syria, Jordan, Iran, Kuwait, and Saudi Arabia. The narrow coastal strip along the Persian Gulf is the country's only outlet to the sea. It is fed by the Tigris and Euphrates rivers and includes ancient Mesopotamia as well as a small part of the Zagros mountain range. Iraq, home to the historical cities of Nineveh and Babylon, is also the cradle of the Sumerian and Babylonian civilizations. Today, Mosul, Baghdad, Basra, Najaf, Tal Afar, Erbil, Tikrit, Samarra, Tuz Khurmatu, Kirkuk, Baqubah, Fallujah, Hilla, Karbala, Diwaniyah, Amarah, and Ramadi are among the important cities. Its capital is Baghdad.

The Development Road Project, which is expected to start in Turkey and cross Iraq from north to south, will reach the Persian Gulf and connect with the Gulf countries. The transit route for this major project is quite important. It has high added value for countries like Turkey, Iraq, and Kuwait. It could also offer opportunities for Saudi Arabia. However, it is at a very serious point in the nationalization and integration of Iraq. Conducting high-standard infrastructure development and integration analyzes based on the Development Road is an important requirement for Iraq.

Turkey's rapprochement with Iraq in the region where Iraq is located will alleviate tensions in the region, foster Turkish-Arab rapprochement, support the region's indigenous development, strengthen agriculture, ensure joint efforts against the global climate crisis and migration, and reduce tensions between Iran, Israel, and Saudi Arabia. This rapprochement will benefit Saudi Arabia and Iran commercially over time. However, from its inception, it provides significant economic benefits to Turkey and Iraq.

Iraq has a very high population growth rate. This trend will continue to increase. Especially among Arabs, this rate is continuously increasing. Here, Central Iraq and Southern Iraq, despite some social differences, are the two main centers of the significant increase in the Arab population. Iran's Khuzestan region is Arab and is a natural continuation of Southern Iraq, equipped with great underground wealth. Iraq, along with Iran, is one of the two important countries neighboring the Persian Gulf.

The development of national and international transportation along the north-south axis in Iraq is quite important for the consolidation of Iraq's national integrity and medium-term transnational integrations. Another step in this direction involves integration with its southern neighbor, Kuwait. Iraq, Kuwait, and Iran's Khuzestan are at the top of the world in terms of the richness of their oil resources. The integration of all this with Turkey is very important and meaningful.

Fig. 1. Big Urbans of Iraq (Britannica Iraq, 2026)

Transport and traffic-related problems and data show some local similarities with Turkey. Italy is similarly affected by an earthquake as Turkey. Vast majority of Italy is on 1st risk degree seismic zone. It has similarities with Turkey in its strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats. Below are the regions of Italy. In Figure 2 Iraq state map is presented (Maps of India Iraq, 2026). Figure 3 shows Iraq Geographical Map (Worldometers Physical Map, 2026). Table 1 shows Iraq cities' populations and liveabilities (OECD, 2020).

Fig. 2. Iraq State Map (Maps of India Iraq/, 2026)

Fig. 3. Iraq Geographical Map (Worldometers Physical Map, 2026)

TABLE 1

IRAQI CITIES POPULATIONS AND RELATED PARAMETERS (OECD

2020)

City	Population	Liveability
Baghdad	8130000	58
Mosul	1790000	52
Suleymaniyah	878000	52
Erbil	846000	51
Najaf	725000	51
Hillah	541000	50
Basra	1330000	48
Ctesiphon	500000	40
Bakubah	468000	39
Abu Ghraib	189000	39

Fallujah	251000	38
Al Karmah	95000	38
Kirkuk	975000	37
Karbala	690000	37
Kufa	171000	37
Ramadi	875000	36
Al Diwaniyah	392000	35
Duhok	331000	35
Samarra	140000	33
Az Zubayr	370000	33
Zakho	219000	33
Kut	378000	32
Nasiriyah	542000	32
Amarah	512000	32
Samawah	215000	32
Tikrit	106000	32
Umm Qasr	108000	31
Al Faw	105000	30
Sinjar	22500	24

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the 21st century, in addition to urbanization, digitalization and sustainability also seem to be at the forefront. What strengthens the trend of digitalization is a continuous and uninterrupted process of technological development and innovation. Western countries have a position to execute on this context. In this parallel, sustainability, digitalization, and urbanization indicate that more investment must be activated on high-speed train network, metro infrastructure, and high-volume inter city bus lines. These mentioned systems can be a initial force for autonomous mobility systems on enhancing nations.

As a developing country in this context, acceleration of well-planned city growth and high capacity transport in Iraq are important dynamics. At the center of all of this, there are well planning, detailed analysis and true approaches (Givoni, 2006).

III. METHODOLOGY

Clustering Analysis

Clustering statistical analysis have been conducted via K means method, PAM and Clara method.

1. K Means Method

Here are results for number of clusters and cluster visulation in terms of K means method in Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Fig. 4. Number of Clusters in Terms of K Means Method

Cluster Visulation

Fig. 5. Cluster Visulation in Terms of K Means Method

2. PAM

Here are results for number of clusters and cluster visulation in terms of PAM in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

Fig. 6. Number of Clusters in Terms of PAM

Cluster Visulation

Fig. 7. Cluster Visulation in Terms of PAM

3. Clara Method

Here are results for number of clusters and cluster visulation in terms of Clara method in Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Fig. 8. Number of Clusters in Terms of Clara Method

Cluster Visulation

Fig. 9. Cluster Visulation in Terms of Clara Method

As a result of all methods and agglomerations, 6 main clusters has emerged for these dataset. On Table 2, clustering list of the cities has been given.

TABLE 2.

CLUSTER LIST OF IRAQI CITIES

City	Population	Cluster
Baghdad	8130000	6
Mosul	1790000	1
Suleymaniyah	878000	4
Erbil	846000	4
Najaf	725000	4
Hillah	541000	4
Basra	1330000	1
Ctesiphon	500000	2
Bakubah	468000	2
Abu Ghraib	189000	2
Fallujah	251000	2
Al Karmah	95000	2
Kirkuk	975000	2
Karbala	690000	2
Kufa	171000	2
Ramadi	875000	2
Al Diwaniyah	392000	2
Duhok	331000	2
Samarra	140000	5
Az Zubayr	370000	5
Zakho	219000	5
Kut	378000	5
Nasiriyah	542000	5
Amarah	512000	5
Samawah	215000	5
Tikrit	106000	5
Umm Qasr	108000	5
Al Faw	105000	5
Sinjar	22500	3

IV. RESULTS

After statistical analysis, prior urbans were gathered on 6-1-4 clusters. On Table 3 selected cities are listed below.

TABLE 3.
SELECTED CITIES VIA CLUSTERING ANALYSE

City	Population	Cluster
Baghdad	8130000	6
Mosul	1790000	1
Suleymaniyah	878000	4
Erbil	846000	4
Najaf	725000	4
Hillah	541000	4
Basra	1330000	1

The cities and urban areas selected above are regions that exhibit Iraq's highest degree of metropolitanization and are trending towards producing the most advanced life quality.

Sustainability, urbanization, and digitalization are the strongest mobility dynamics of the 21st century. These dynamics can best take place on developing nations and regions too. Sustainable transportation, reducing traffic congestion, increasing traffic safety, decreasing noise and air pollution, expanding railway investments, advancing autonomous vehicle technologies, equipping infrastructure facilities with current advanced technologies, and the integrated renewal of cities are the most important aspects of modern transportation and urbanization (Kiziltas, 2020).

Along with emerging technology, there are many alternative modes of transportation that provide high-quality service at high inter-city speeds. These can be classified as magnetically driven trains (Maglev), high-speed trains, airlines, high-comfort road transport. These modes of transport are highly competitive in cross-city travel, but their interconnections are combined or isolated accordingly.

- Competitiveness
- Integration
- Residence instead of each other
- Transformative transportation

These modes of transportation involve the priority, integration or substitution of cities according to their size, human characteristics, demand for transportation, urban features, interconnected spatial and technical locations, requirements, distances between cities and a number of fundamental parameters. Among the various cities in Western Europe, this is the case with high-speed trains and airlines (Marta et al, 2010).

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this context, Figure 10 shows high-speed mobility proposal map of Iraq.

Fig. 10. High Speed Mobility Proposal Regions on Map (Red Legend: Proposals)

Iraq is one of the most important countries in the Arab world. It is also important for Arab history, Turkish history, and Islamic history. The country, which is also home to ancient civilizations, was part of the Ottoman Empire in the pre-modern period. While a significant portion of their lands was part of Ottoman Turkey, the majority was administered under the central provinces of the Ottoman Empire. Iraq experienced its early modernization under Ottoman rule. In the modern era, the province of Mosul, the province of Baghdad, and the province of Basra within the Ottoman Empire merged to form the country

and state of Iraq as it exists today. Today, the cities of Baghdad, Mosul, and Basra, which are the capitals of the aforementioned provinces, rank among the largest cities in Iraq. The development of high-speed transportation, air travel, and inland waterway transportation should be considered in Iraq. The holistic development of all these systems will also strengthen integration with Turkey.

As shown in the map, the cities selected in terms of deep analysis in this study are clustered mostly on north-south main axis of the country that have most central and densely populated cities of Iraq. On the other hand, with the completion of all the proposed planning and execution of Development Road (Kalkınma Yolu) a big integration will occur on south-north axis of Iraq from Tel Afar, Mosul, Erbil, Kirkuk, Tuzhurmatu (Sala ad-Din), Baghdad, Babil to Basra. There will be a big development on Mid Iraq and South Iraq for Arab communities. Also transforming to province of Tuzhurmatu and Tel Afar Turkmen cities will be suitable for efficient management.

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